

Flood Hazard and Risk Mapping by applying an Explainable Machine Learning Framework using Satellite Imagery and GIS data

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Abstract: Flood is one of the most destructive natural phenomena that happens world-widely leading to damage of properties, infrastructures, or even loss of lives. The escalation in intensity and number of flooding events as a result of the combination of climate change and anthropogenic factors motivates the need to adopt real-time solutions for mapping flood hazards and risks. In this study, a methodological framework is proposed that enables the assessment of flood hazard and risk levels of severity dynamically by fusing optical remote sensing (Sentinel-1) and GIS-based data from the region of Trieste, Monfalcone and Muggia Municipalities. Explainable machine learning techniques were utilised, aiming to interpret the results for the assessment of flood hazard. The flood inventory was randomly divided into 70% were used for training and the remaining 30% were employed for testing. Various combinations of the models were evaluated for the assessment of flood hazard. The results revealed that the Random Forest model achieved the highest F1-score (approx. 0.99), among others and utilised for generating flood hazard maps. Furthermore, the estimation of the flood risk achieved by a combination of a rule-based approach to estimate the exposure and vulnerability with the dynamic assessment of flood hazard.

Keywords: Flood Hazard; Flood Risk Maps; Flood Susceptibility; Satellite Imagery analysis; Crisis Maps; Machine Learning

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1. Introduction

Over the past couple of decades, flood disasters are intensified, become more frequent and are more destructive compared with the old ones, especially in the developing countries, such as those in Latin America and the Caribbean [1], causing loss of human lives and properties worldwide. According to the CRED's Emergency Events Database (EM-DAT¹), 44% of all disaster events from 2000 to 2019 concern flooding events, that have impacted on 1.6 billion people worldwide, which is the highest figure for any disaster type. Furthermore, floods are the most common type of event with an average of 163 events per year [2]. Climate changes along with anthropogenic factors play a significant role in escalating the severe impacts of flood disasters in terms of economic loss, social disruptions, and damage to the urban environment. Therefore, the proper monitoring to identify areas prone to floods and the effective mitigation countermeasures are considered very important to risk reduction [3–7].

The deployment of real-time solutions for mapping flood hazard and the estimation of potential consequences of flood events might be extremely valuable towards con-

¹ <https://www.emdat.be/>

32 fronting emergency response and mitigating the impact of those events [8]. Therefore,
33 realising the need for effective flood management, the European Union adopted Euro-
34 pean Directive 2007/60 / EC on flood risk assessment and management, which entered
35 into force on 26 November 2007. In this Directive, the flood mapping was considered as
36 a crucial element of flood risk management and moreover, it requested from EU Member
37 States to prepare two types of crisis maps, namely the flood hazard and risk maps, by
38 2013 (art 6) and update them every six years [9,10].

39 *Flood mapping* is a process that describes the expected extent of Track changes is
40 on 6 water inundation into dryland as a result of intense precipitation or river water
41 level rise driven by natural or anthropogenic factors [11]. Although, flood mapping
42 basically comprising of flood hazard maps and flood risk maps, however, it processes
43 vary considerably from project to project, and/or country to country, depending on
44 specific project requirements and country-specific guideline, legislation etc. [9,10,12,13].
45 Flood mapping provides the baseline for a good understanding of historical flood trends,
46 future expectations, and identification of vulnerable - susceptible locations likely to
47 be impacted by flooding. Hence, the flood hazard and risk maps are considered as
48 important tools to communicate flood risk to various target groups [12]. They convey the
49 compiled information for flooding events to relevant public bodies like civil protection
50 and water management authorities, municipalities and local states or disaster/crisis
51 managers and control staffs, but also raise awareness to the broad public [14].

52 Recently, the hazard, exposure and vulnerability from natural disasters have been
53 assessed by utilising machine learning methods in a descriptive and/or predictive man-
54 ner. Descriptive Machine Learning methods focus on the Response and Recovery phases
55 of the Disaster Management Cycle while the Predictive Machine Learning methods
56 concentrate to provide forecasting assessments of a natural disaster, enhancing the
57 preparedness and mitigation processes of the Disaster Management Cycle [5,6,15,16].

58 Specifically, flood hazard assessments employing descriptive machine learning
59 methodologies focus primarily on the response phase, by estimating current inundation
60 extents and depths. The aim is to provide assistance in various levels: to emergency
61 responders and those affected directly, as well as to public and government authorities
62 assessing the impact of the event. The increasing volume of obtained data due to
63 the rise of Earth Observation technologies, such as Synthetic Aperture Radar - SAR
64 (e.g. Sentinel 1) and optical data (e.g. Sentinel 2), as well as social media, provides
65 opportunities for machine learning methods to improve efficiency of existing flood
66 detection approaches [5,6,15,17,18]. Satellite remote sensing capabilities have been
67 utilised to monitor for timely and near-real-time flood disaster detection. Specifically,
68 SAR technology overcomes the limitations of the remotely sensed optical data which are
69 not functional during cloud-cover or at night and as a result enhances total temporal
70 resolution [6,7,15,17–19]. Advanced machine learning classification methods can be used
71 to improve the process of the flood extend assessment and consequently the severity
72 level of a flood hazard. However, the creation of these models requires the existence of
73 annotated datasets to be used as training sets.

74 As stated in [5] one of the main key research challenges in this domain is the lack
75 of large scale annotation datasets, related to social media and satellite sensing data, for
76 training and evaluation machine learning models enable to detect and analyse disasters
77 generated by natural extreme events. Moreover, Said et al. [5] pointed out that another
78 open issue in the application of Remote Sensing Disaster Management cycle concerns
79 the Satellite Imagery low temporal frequency. On the other hand, time is vital during
80 a disaster event in order to enable authorities to respond effectively to minimise the
81 socio-economic, ecologic, and cultural impact of the event, to evacuate vulnerable people
82 at risk, and general for recovery processes [20].

83 Motivated by the above limitations, the main contribution in this work is the
84 adoption of a methodological framework for the creation in near real-time of flood
85 hazard and risk maps that is relied on the fusion of the satellite imagery outcomes

86 and the GIS-based data. Explainable Machine Learning techniques are employed to
87 analyse and aggregate the information in a pixel-based approach aiming to estimate
88 the flood hazard in terms of the severity levels, namely moderate, medium and high
89 hazard. A thorough analysis of the specific local characteristics in pixel-based operation
90 enhances the reliability of the proposed framework regarding the classification of these
91 small areas in terms of their severity level. The annotation of the datasets which are
92 needed for the modeling phase is carried out in an automated way, performing a rule
93 that relies on the experts' knowledge. Furthermore, relied on a rule-based approach, the
94 assessment of the exposure, vulnerability as well as flood risk are carried out producing
95 the corresponding crisis maps. Hence, the proposed framework enables authorities and
96 other crisis managers to reliable map and monitor flooding events by generating crisis
97 maps almost dynamically, which are strengthening situational awareness providing an
98 adequate picture of the crisis.

99 2. Relevant Literature

100 Recently, numerous studies have been proposed to create flood susceptibility maps
101 as a tool for efficient flood risk management [21–30]. Flood susceptibility indicates the
102 propensity of an area, given by its physical-geographical characteristics, to be affected
103 by flooding. Additionally, flood susceptibility mapping can be determined as a quan-
104 titative and qualitative assessment of an area with likely flood occurrence, providing
105 simultaneously the spatial distribution of the particular natural event [22,26]. Since
106 the analysis and the mapping of flood susceptibility identify the most vulnerable areas
107 and therefore can be considered as one of the most important aspects of early warning
108 systems or strategies for prevention and mitigation of future flood situations [28,31]. It
109 should be mentioned that apart from flood hazard, also the vulnerability and exposure
110 can be visualised as maps, therefore, they are spatially explicit and are integrated into a
111 GIS context. For instance, in a grid cell of GIS maps of a certain size, we can explicitly
112 exhibit the expected depth of a flood and the presence of buildings and people and the
113 likelihood of them to be damaged or harmed.

114 With the rise of technological advances in Remote Sensing, Geographic Information
115 System and Machine Learning, multidisciplinary approaches have been proposed aiming
116 to efficiently map, monitor and manage floods. Hence, in the flood risk assessment,
117 multiple satellite-based flood mapping and monitoring can be considered as an essential
118 and imperative process. By leveraging the increasing availability of free-of-charge or
119 low-cost satellite data with global coverage (e.g. Sentinel-1 and -2 from ESA, and Landsat
120 and MODIS satellites from NASA) [32], new potentialities have emerged in the near
121 real-time for mapping and modeling flood risk and its impact assessments [33]. As a
122 result, authorities and stakeholders can be assisted to carry out appropriate disaster
123 response and relief activities achieving in the early stages the disaster risk reduction and
124 mitigation [34]. Another low-cost Remote Sensing solution that has gained considerable
125 interest in the last decades is the Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) [35,36]. Equipped
126 by high-resolution camera sensors, UAVs can capture high-quality topographical data
127 and facilitate monitoring and mapping a natural hazardous event [37].

128 Advanced machine learning methods coupled with multi-criteria analysis methods
129 and remote sensing technologies have been developed and applied effectively in flood
130 susceptibility mapping. To name of a few, in [22] the performance of four machine-
131 learning methods, namely Kernel Logistic Regression, Radial Basis Function Classifier,
132 Multinomial Naïve Bayes, and Logistic Model Tree have been compared in terms of their
133 efficiency to create reliable flash flood susceptibility maps. Similar, in [23] novel hybrid
134 computational approaches of machine learning methods for flash flood susceptibility
135 mapping, namely AdaBoostM1 based Credal Decision Tree, Bagging based Credal Deci-
136 sion Tree, Dagging based Credal Decision Tree, MultiBoostAB based Credal Decision
137 Tree, and single Credal Decision Tree have been compared for flash flood susceptibility
138 assessment. In [24] authors focused on Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and applied

139 various kernels to investigate their capabilities to assess accurately the flood suscep-
140 tibility and produce the corresponding mappings. Logistic Regression (LR) has been
141 employed in [25] aiming to determine the significance of flood conditioning factors to
142 flood susceptibility. Researchers in [21] adopted an approach to identify the areas sus-
143 ceptible to flash-flooding, by relying on the computation of Flash-Flood Potential Index
144 (FFPI) and using two machine learning models (k-Nearest Neighbor and K-Star) along
145 with their novel ensemble with an Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). Furthermore,
146 in [26] an approach to derive an integrated model, considering the best performing
147 models among the combinations of four models: Artificial Neural Network (ANN), AHP,
148 LR, and Frequency Ratio (FR) have been proposed. The goal was to develop a unique
149 flood hazard map of Bangladesh by increasing the precision of flood susceptibility as-
150 sessments. In [38] a hybrid model comprising Principal Component Analysis, LR and
151 Frequency Distribution analyses has been presented, while in [39] an ensemble modeling
152 approach which incorporates the SVM with Multivariate Discriminant Analysis (MDA),
153 and Classification and Regression Trees (CART) to create a flood susceptibility maps
154 has been proposed. Another ensemble method that combines SVM using a radial basis
155 function kernel with the FR approach to estimate flood probability has recently pro-
156 posed [40]. The ultimate goal was to assess the flood risk. In [41] two machine learning
157 techniques, namely, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and SVM fused to develop
158 most reliable flood susceptibility maps using GIS data. In [42] authors proposed a Deep
159 Neural Network (DNN) model that employed Sentinel-1 satellite data by fusing the SAR
160 backscatter coefficients and the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) data, so as to generate
161 water-bodies masks.

162 Generally, in the majority of the above studies, the satellite imagery and GIS related
163 data are provided in near real-time in order to assess the risk of an extreme flood event
164 which is in progress.

165 **3. Materials and Methods**

166 *3.1. Study Area*

167 The study domain is located in North-East of Italy, and specifically in the eastern
168 part of Friuli Venezia Giulia Region and of the Eastern Alps River Basin District, close
169 to the boundary between Italy and Slovenia. In particular, this work focuses on three
170 distinct areas, each of them located in a different Municipality, namely Trieste, Muggia
171 and Monfalcone, as it is illustrated in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Location of the case study areas (the square boxes). The coordinates are expressed in the Reference system WGS84 - EPSG 4326

172 The area of Trieste and Muggia is unique in Italy from a hydrogeological perspec-
 173 tive, having karst features and thus lacking of surface hydrography and well-defined
 174 watersheds. As regards the topography, these two Municipalities are characterized by
 175 the presence of steep hillside close to the shoreline, as can be seen from the elevation
 176 plotted in Figure 2. However, the urban centers of the two municipalities, where this
 177 work focuses, have a low elevation, close to the sea level. As regards the Monfalcone
 178 region, the Municipality is mostly located in the plain called in Italian 'Pianura Isontina',
 179 at the mouth of the Isonzo River. The elevation of the area is very close, if not inferior, to
 180 the sea level and the terrain mostly plain with very low slope (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Elevation of the case study area in meters above sea level. Referred to vertical Datum EPSG 32632 (WGS84/UTM Zone 32), while the horizontal coordinates are expressed in the Geographic Reference System WGS84 - EPSG 4326 (Source of data INGV <http://tinitaly.pi.ingv.it/>, elaborated by AAWA)

181 Due to the fact that the all the three study areas are characterized by low elevation
 182 of the ground above sea level, they are particularly prone to floods due to high tides
 183 of the Adriatic sea triggered by meteorological conditions. In fact, Flood hazard in the
 184 coastal area often manifests trough storm surge simultaneous to with specific climate
 185 conditions (rainfall, high tide, southern winds). Flooding in the urban areas of Trieste
 186 and Muggia is caused, in addition to the topography, by the excessive imperviousness
 187 of the soil and because of the difficult discharge of the superficial runoff when high tide
 188 is simultaneous to the flow of the superficial drainage network [43]. In addition, for the
 189 area of Muggia, even if the karst geology mostly causes the lack of superficial water
 190 bodies, there are two streams: Rosandra and Ospò. These two streams highlight some
 191 critical points from hydraulic point of view, due to the insufficient maintenance and to
 192 the increasing pluvial runoff caused by the intensive urbanization.

193 Regarding Monfalcone area, the territory, located in the east side of the Isonzo River,
 194 is well known to be humid (swampland). In particular, drainage network often shows
 195 failures in occasion of flood events simultaneous with high tides. As it can be seen from
 196 Figure 2, part of the territory has also an elevation lower than the mean sea level. In
 197 addition, the area presents a relevant underground hydrography (e.g. the Karst river
 198 Timavo). Thus, in this area high tide can cause flooding due to the insufficiency of the
 199 marine levees, as well as for overflowing of the drainage network [43]. Finally, for the
 200 Monfalcone area, the flood risk is due also by the presence of the Isonzo River, one of
 201 the most important rivers for the Eastern Alps River Basin District, as well as its most
 202 relevant transboundary water body. The Isonzo River originates in Trenta's valley with
 203 springs at an altitude of 935 m and flows into the Adriatic sea, near Monfalcone, where
 204 it forms a delta that tends, over time, to move from West to East. The Isonzo catchment
 205 basin subtends a total area of approximately 3400 km² of which is about 1150 km², that
 206 is about one third, in Italian territory. The Isonzo river, as character purely torrential,
 207 collects and discharges the waters of the southern side of the Alps Giulie, which separate

208 this basin from that of the Sava. The main right tributaries are the Coritenza, in Slovenian
 209 territory, and the Torre, which flows almost entirely in the Italian part. On the left, the
 210 Isonzo is fed by Idria and Vipacco, with their respective basins included totally and
 211 almost totally in Slovenian territory [44].

212 3.1.1. Digital Elevation Model in the Study Area

213 The Digital Elevation Model (DEM) has been provided by Eastern Alps River Basin
 214 District Authority (AAWA), who performed some GIS elaborations on the official DEM
 215 of the Friuli Venezia Giulia Region. DEM is provided into the reference system UTM 33N
 216 (EPSG 3045). It has been obtained using Laser Imaging, Detection And Ranging (LIDAR)
 217 technique from a set of areal flights which were performed in 2019. The raw data
 218 obtained from the flights (a cloud of points) has been gradually processed to provide the
 219 final product. This, in turn, consists of a representation of the points of terrain, devoid of
 220 all the elements above the ground (like buildings, vegetation, cables etc.), on a regular
 221 grid with pixel resolution of $0.5\text{ m} \times 0.5\text{ m}$, divided between many different tiles. The
 222 DEM has a planimetric accuracy of 0.15 m and an altimetric one which ranges from
 223 0.15 m (in open field) and 0.3 m (under vegetation cover), both estimated through a set of
 224 reference points all over the region. It should be noted that for the city of Trieste, which
 225 is particular vulnerable to floods caused by the tide, identify flat areas near the sea is
 226 thus very important. We used three areas with DEM resolution equal to 0.5 m as shown
 227 in the above figure (Figure 2).

228 3.2. Flood Conditioning Factors

229 Floods are natural phenomena, caused by many different factors, including clima-
 230 tology, hydrology, geomorphology, topography and land use. For the purpose of this
 231 work, topography and land use are considered, extracting some of the most relevant
 232 conditioning factors from DEM analysis, well-known as *Flood Conditioning Factors*. The
 233 application of accurate Remote Sensing techniques is essential for obtaining reliable
 234 DEM and consequently more accurate factors. Furthermore, equivalent spatial resolution
 235 should be employed to calculate these factors. Below, a brief description of the factors
 236 that we utilised in this work is exhibited.

237 **Elevation:** the elevation of the terrain has a great influence on floods. Firstly, at a
 238 great scale, the dynamic of the event is usually completely different in high elevation
 239 areas (mountains) than low elevation ones (i.e. plains) which usually are more vulnerable
 240 to flooding caused by various reasons such as river overtopping, drainage system failure
 241 and/or rising water level of seas, or other water bodies. Secondly, at a minor scale,
 242 the terrain elevation determines the presence of preferential pathways, which channels
 243 the superficial runoff, or accumulation areas, which usually are represented by local
 244 depression of the terrain.

245 **Slope** is an essential factor for studying flash flood susceptibility because it affects
 246 the speed of water. Slope of a line can be positive, negative, nil, etc. [27].

247 **Aspect** is related to the directions of water flow affecting flash flood occurrence.
 248 Flat areas are more vulnerable to water accumulation and/or spreading of water over
 249 a large surface, in particular when large volumes of water are involved. Therefore, by
 250 using this parameter, the flat regions can easily be identified [23,27].

251 **Topographic Wetness Index (TWI)** is a topo-hydrological factor and reflects the
 252 wetness potential of each pixel. It can be calculated as a fraction of flow accumulation,
 253 A_s , and the slope α (in degree) at the pixel:

$$254 \quad TWI = \ln \frac{A_s}{\tan \alpha} \quad (1)$$

255 The increment of the TWI index, indicating higher wetness characteristics, means
 256 that high flow accumulation carries out in low slope surfaces, and, therefore, potentially
 257 indicates locations that are exposed at greater flood hazard [21,23–25,45].

257 **Topographic Position Index (TPI)** is a ratio of the pixel elevation (grid cell) and the
 258 mean elevation of its neighboring pixels (cells) respectively [21,45]:

$$TPI = \frac{E_{pixel}}{E_{surrounding}} \quad (2)$$

259 **Terrain Ruggedness Index (TRI)** is in contrast to the TWI and is responsible for
 260 quantifying ruggedness of the terrain, by portraying the local variance of surface gra-
 261 dients or curvatures. TRI is considered as a morphometric measure that describes the
 262 heterogeneous condition of a land surface and facilitates characterizing it as smooth or
 263 rugged [27]. TRI which is defined as the mean difference between a central pixel and its
 264 surrounding cells can be calculated as follows [45]:

$$TRI = \sqrt{|x|(max^2 - min^2)} \quad (3)$$

265 where x shows the elevation of each neighbor cell to cell $(0,0)(m)$. In addition, min
 266 and max reflect the smallest and largest elevation value among nine neighbor pixels,
 267 respectively.

268 **Land Use Land Cover (LULC)** is considered an efficient and important factor which
 269 be associated with flooding [24–26,28]. It can be concluded that under different LULC
 270 patterns the runoff conditions can be varied. Natural types of land cover differ in
 271 terms of infiltration capacity, while anthropogenic environments such as built-up areas,
 272 plantations, agricultural fields, or deforested areas also diverse. In vegetated areas,
 273 the runoff is minor due to the greater capacity of infiltration of the soil, which helps
 274 to mitigate the effect of a flood than in urban areas, where are typically composed of
 275 impermeable surfaces and increased surface runoff, and thus the infiltration rate is very
 276 low [24–26,28]. In this work, we employ the Corine Land Cover (CLC) map to estimate
 277 the Manning Roughness coefficient, as well as the presence of exposed assets for risk
 278 evaluation. CLC is a consistent classification system of long-term land cover data in
 279 Europe. The dataset gives detailed information about Land Cover for 44 classes, some of
 280 which are defined as mixed land cover and land use classes, with a thematic accuracy
 281 more than 85%.

282 **Water Velocity** is another factor that along with water depth directly affects the
 283 flood occurrence. It is determined by combining the *Water Depth* (h), *Slope* (S), *Manning*
 284 *Roughness* (n) *coefficient* and *pixel Resolution* (L), based on the following formula:

$$v_i = \frac{1}{n_i} \sqrt{S_i} \left(\frac{h_i L}{2h_i + L} \right)^{2/3} \quad (4)$$

285 where:

- 286 v_i denotes the Water Velocity (in m/s) at the i -th pixel;
- 287 h_i denotes the Water Depth (in m) at the i -th pixel;
- 288 S_i denotes the slope (in decimals) per pixel;
- 289 L denotes the resolution (in m) of each pixel;
- 290 n_i denotes the Manning Roughness (Gauckler–Manning–Strickler) coefficient (in
 291 $s/m^{1/3}$), that depends also on the land use and thus can be related by the Corine
 292 Land Cover index, indicating the surface roughness per pixel.

293 3.3. Satellite Imagery Analysis

294 For the flood detection we processed the Sentinel-1 GRD-IW products of the flooded
 295 day and the timeseries images using ESA's Sentinel Application Platform² (SNAP).
 296 Following preprocessing steps were applied [46]:

² <https://step.esa.int/main/toolboxes/snap/>

- 297 • **Apply Orbit File:** The operation of applying a precise orbit available in SNAP
298 allows the automatic download and update of the orbit state vectors for each SAR
299 scene in its product metadata, providing an accurate satellite position and velocity
300 information.
- 301 • **Thermal Noise Removal:** Reduces noise effects in the inter-sub-swath texture, in
302 particular, normalizing the backscatter signal within the entire Sentinel-1 scene and
303 resulting in reduced discontinuities between sub-swaths for scenes in multi-swath
304 acquisition modes.
- 305 • **Subset:** the initial product is cropped so it contains only the lake we want to observe.
306 Some balance between the inundated and non-inundated areas is desired.
- 307 • **Radiometric calibration:** Fixes the uncertainty in the radiometric resolution of
308 satellite sensor. *The pixel values can be directly related to the radar backscatter of the scene.*
309 The information required to apply the calibration equation is included within the
310 Sentinel-1 GRD product.
- 311 • **Speckle noise removal:** Removes the pepper and salt like pattern noise that is
312 caused by the interference of electromagnetic waves. The “Lee Sigma” filter of Lee
313 (1981) [47] with a 5×5 filter size is used to filter the intensity data. As noted by
314 Jong-Sen Lee et al. (2009) [48], this step is essential in almost any analysis of radar
315 images, due to the speckle noise aggravation of the interpretation process.
- 316 • **Terrain correction:** Projects the pixels onto a map system (WGS84 was selected) and
317 re-sampled to a 10m spatial resolution. Also, topographic corrections with a Shuttle
318 Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) digital elevation model (DEM) is performed.
319 Corrects the distortions over the areas of the terrain.
- 320 • **Linear to Decibel (dB):** The dynamic range of the backscatter intensity of the
321 transmitted radar signal values is usually a few orders of magnitudes. Thus, these
322 values are converted from linear scale to logarithmic scale leading to an easier to
323 manipulate histogram, also making water and dry areas more distinctive.

324 The analysis of the obtained Sentinel-1 images that are extracted from the Coperni-
325 cus Open Access Hub (previously known as Sentinels Scientific Data Hub), carried out
326 in order to estimate the Water-bodies Masks (water delineation maps). Particularly, we
327 perform histogram thresholding on the processed VH band of the Area of Interest (AoI).
328 The deep valley of the histogram separates the inundated from the non-inundated areas.
329 This thresholding technique works better when there is adequate number of inundated
330 areas in order to distinguish them from the dry ones, otherwise threshold extraction may
331 fail. In the satellite images of the areas that we study it is quite common that water
332 and land areas are not in balance. Thus, in order to increase the chance to estimate a
333 valid threshold we split the image to nine (9) tiles and then perform the thresholding
334 to each one of them, calculating eventually the average threshold that is used in the
335 whole image to separate the inundated from the non-inundated areas. This pixel-based
336 classification of the region of interest, will be fused with the information from DEM to
337 estimate the Water Depth. For each separate water body (sub-area) of a water mask,
338 the maximum elevation is detected using the DEM. Then, for this sub-area the Water
339 Depth is estimated by subtracting each pixel DEM value from the maximum elevation. It
340 should be noted, that flood depth along with flood duration directly contribute to flood
341 occurrence [26].

342 3.4. Machine Learning techniques

343 In this work, we utilised a well-known machine learning techniques for classifica-
344 tion, namely Support Vector Machines (SVMs), Naive Bayes (NB), an ensemble learning
345 method called Random Forest (RF) and a feed-forward Neural Network (NN). A brief
346 description of them is the following:

- 347 • **Support Vector Machine - SVM:** Support Vector Machine (SVM) Classifier [49]
348 represents a supervised machine learning technique that exploits the abilities of
349 hyperplanes, reshaping the nonlinear world into linear in order to classify the

- 350 features. Hyperplane is a decision plane that aims to separate a set of objects and
 351 label them into different classes. SVM consists a method which is aiming to separate
 352 in more efficient way the features using hyperplanes.
- 353 • **Naive Bayes - NB:** According to Bayes Theorem, we deployed the statistical classifica-
 354 tion technique, Naïve Bayes (NB) classifier. This classifier belongs into the group
 355 of supervised learning algorithms and happens to be one of the simplest with high
 356 accuracy and speed, especially when it collocates with large datasets. NB is using a
 357 classifier model which is assigning class labels into the problem events, represented
 358 as vectors of feature events, where a set is used to annotate the class labels.
 - 359 • **Random Forest - RF:** The Random Forest (RF) [50] is a well-known ensemble
 360 machine learning method either for classification or regression. The objective of this
 361 classification technique is to compare and analyze the dataset variables to define
 362 new weights for each factor. In our case of study, the RF model exploits decision
 363 trees in order to calculate and estimate the connection between Flood Hazard Index
 364 labeling and Flood feature factors values, focusing on the end to classify each vector
 365 of values into a predicted label. RF is simple, fast, able to handle large datasets, it
 366 has generally high outcome through randomization and is applicable to multiclass
 367 algorithm characteristics.
 - 368 • **Neural Network - NN:** Neural Networks can be portrayed as the hierarchical
 369 multilevel relationships between neurons in a network of neurons similar to the
 370 function of the brain. The neurons implement a feedback mechanism with each
 371 other, transmitting the necessary signals to the next levels, based on the received
 372 input received from the respective previous levels, reaching one or more final
 373 results.

374 3.5. Model evaluation metrics

- 375 • **Confusion matrix:** Confusion Matrix is a table (Table 1) that presents the results
 376 from classifiers, using some specific terms, such as “True positives (TP)” “the pre-
 377 dicted and actually positive result, “False positives (FP)” the predicted positive but
 378 actually negative result, “True negatives (TN)” the predicted and actually negative
 379 result and “False negatives (FN)” the predicted negative but actually positives.

Table 1. Confusion matrix representation.

	Actually Positive	Actually Negative
Predicted Positive	True Positives (TPs)	False Positives (FPs)
Predicted Negative	False Negatives (FNs)	True Negatives (TNs)

- **Accuracy:** Accuracy is the most commonly percentage metric for machine learning models judging the accuracy of the results and can me calculated using confusion matrix terms:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN} \quad (5)$$

- **Precision:** Precision answers the question of what analogy of the positive results was in fact correct and can be calculated using:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (6)$$

- **Recall:** Recall on the other hand, answers the question of what analogy of true positives was identified correctly and can be calculated using:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (7)$$

- **F1-score:** F1-Score is a measure to evaluate classification systems and is a way to combine the precision and recall results. It can be described as the harmonic mean of precision and recall and can be calculated using:

$$F1 - Score = \frac{2 * Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (8)$$

- **Cross-Validation k-fold:** Cross-validation is a statistical method of evaluating machine learning models, where it divides the dataset into random K-segments in order to use them for model training and comparing them we select the best model. The process of cross-validation, has a single parameter k, which refers to the number of segments that will randomly separate each set of data. In our case k is equal to 10 and we choose the best model using the average result per training.

4. Methodology

In the case of extreme natural events, such as floods, the hazard, exposure and vulnerability can be identified when interactions between these events and human societies are assessed. Flood Hazard can be estimated from the physical characteristics of the flood event such as the extent, water depth, persistence, and flow velocity. The hazard outcome is a map of flood intensity, provided by the hydrological analysis and modelling i.e., flood frequency analysis, geomorphological characteristics of the region under assessment (pathway) and manufactured barriers against the hazard (attenuation) elements of the assessed area. Conventionally approaches consider different return times and measures of intensity, producing multiple hazard maps [13,14].

Furthermore, the exposure refers to the characteristics of the people and assets that can be affected by flooding, focusing mainly on the social, environmental and economic value of them. Vulnerability is the human dimension of flood disasters and is the result of the range of economic, social, cultural, institutional, political, and psychological factors. The physical component is captured by the likelihood that receptors located in the area considered, could potentially be harmed (susceptibility of receptors). The social one is the ex-ante preparedness of society given their risk perception of awareness to combat hazard and reduce its adverse impact or their ex-post skills to overcome the hazard damages and return to the initial state (represented by adaptive and coping capacities). These can increase the susceptibility of an individual, a community, assets, or systems to the impacts of flood hazards [51–53].

The proposed framework tailors the definition for the disaster risk which was defined in 2017 by the UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNISDR) and includes the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 [53,54]. Therefore, *Disaster Risk (R)* is defined as the potential loss of life, injury, or destroyed or damaged assets which could occur to a system, society, or a community in a specific period of time, determined probabilistically as a function of hazard, exposure, vulnerability and capacity. Based on the above term, in the field of natural hazards, the disaster risk results from the coupling between hazard (H), vulnerability (V) and exposure (E):

$$Disaster Risk = f(Hazard, Vulnerability, Exposure) \quad (9)$$

In our approach, the severity level of the flood hazard is dynamically assessed by employing machine learning techniques that are able to multimodal fuse data generated by the analysis of Sentinel-1 images and GIS-based data. Then, a rule-based approach is utilised in order to estimate in near real-time the vulnerability and the exposure in the region of interest. Specifically, the proposed framework consists of ten (10) successive steps as illustrated in the following figure (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Flowchart of the Dynamic Flood Hazard Assessment Algorithm.

421 The first two steps concern the specification of the area of interest and the choice of
 422 dates where flood events were carried out. The essential condition is the existence of the
 423 satellite images from the study area. Steps 3-7 concern the processes for the creation of
 424 flood hazard maps in near real-time, when new satellite images appear for the particular
 425 area. The water mask, water depth and velocity of the water body along with other
 426 flood conditioning factors which are derived from the analysis of satellite imagery or
 427 extracted from GIS tools, are fused by employing machine learning techniques. As a
 428 result, is the generation in near real-time flood hazard maps that highlight the areas that
 429 are affected by or are vulnerable to a potential flood hazard.

430 The remaining steps concern the assessment of vulnerabilities, exposure upon
 431 three main categories concerning the people, economic activities, and environment,
 432 cultural-archaeological assets and protected areas. A rule-based approach has utilised
 433 for this purpose. In the last step, the combination of the assessments of the hazard,
 434 vulnerabilities and exposure generates the hydraulic risk. In the following sections, the
 435 steps of the proposed methodological framework are described in more details.

436 4.1. Dynamic Flood Hazard Assessment Algorithm

437 The proposed approach for Dynamic Flood Hazard Assessment consists of seven
 438 (7) steps as they are illustrated in the Figure 3. Specifically, a study of the area of
 439 interest should be realised including the gathering of appropriate information from
 440 past extreme flood events. Then, the data acquisition phase should be taken place and
 441 the appropriate features are extracted from the data aiming to create a dataset for the
 442 application of machine learning methods. The obtained data should be homogenised
 443 and pre-processed so as to deal with missing values or outliers, data impurity issues,
 444 different ranges over the features, etc. Hence, a flood inventory will be created that
 445 contains data suitable for apply Machine Learning modeling. In the training/testing
 446 phase machine learning models will be fit to the data and evaluate their performance
 447 in terms of their accuracy. The best machine learning model is chosen and utilised in
 448 Validation phase to create the flood hazard maps.

4.1.1. Study Area and Historical Flood Events

As aforementioned (Section 3.1) the area of interest to further study is located in the municipality of Trieste. For this particular region, past flood events were chosen in dates that there are satellite imagery that captured the events.

4.1.2. Data Acquisition and Feature Extraction

The processes of data collection and feature extraction aiming to create adequate feature space that will be utilised in the modelling phase are included in this step. The data will be gathered from two diverse sources (Figure 3), namely from the analysis of satellite images and the DEM.

The Sentinel-1 Images (SAR) were analysed by employing the preprocessing steps that were described in the Section 3.3. Their spatial resolution was equal to 10m and temporal resolution was approximately 6 days or less. The outcome of these steps undergoes a histogram thresholding analysis that generates the appropriate water masks.

The Flood Conditioning Factors that are employed in this work derived from the DEM as described in Section 3.2. Each one of these factors can be considered as an independent feature in the feature space. As they are provided as maps, they can be converted to raster image (format) with pixel size which is equal to the pixel size of the DEM. In this way, all the images will obtain the same resolution. Then, a feature space of nine (9) attributes (features) are formulated, in which each feature corresponds to one raster image. The number of entries in the dataset depends on the total number of pixels in each image (*width x height*).

4.1.3. Data Preprocessing

The dataset that has generated after the fusion of all the features, as it was described in the above section, should be subdue under preprocessing procedures including the followings:

- **Create annotated dataset:** Upgrade the data set by adding a target variable so that Machine Learning techniques can be applied. Our goal is to create machine learning models enable to assess the flood hazard level and which are relied on the flood conditioning factors and the real-time analysis of satellite imagery. Hence, the target-variable should be the "Flood Hazard" that receives three potential values, namely Moderate (Low) Hazard, Medium Hazard and High Hazard. To be annotated the dataset, the following rule will be applied [44,55]:

If $WaterVelocity < 1m/s$ and $0m < WaterDepth < 1m$ Then Moderate Hazard
Else If $WaterVelocity < 1m/s$ and $WaterDepth \geq 1m$ Then Medium Hazard
Else If $WaterVelocity \geq 1m/s$ and $WaterDepth > 0m$ Then High Hazard

It should be mentioned here that the above rule is based on hypothesis of medium probability of the flood, which has a 100-year return period in the study area.

- **Handle Imbalanced dataset:** due to the facts that inundated areas usually are a quite small portion of the whole region of interest and furthermore floods are a quite rare extreme event, then it is expected the majority of entries in the "Flood Hazard" will belong to the Moderate Hazard class causing an imbalanced dataset. Hence, the machine learning models will be biased to the majority class. To tackle with this issue a random sampling is performed, and a portion of the majority class is selected equal to the amount of data that belong to the other two classes.
- **Handle missing or extreme values:** pixels with missing values or extreme values that indicate areas that are out of the interest, e.g. inside the sea, should be detected and removed from the analysis.
- **Data Normalisation:** the aim is to eliminate the numerical differences between the features and transform them to the same range. Machine learning models require that the input data are normalized using the same range, since the bias may occur in the results due to the bigger magnitude of the initial untransformed data.

Hence, the min-max scaler is utilised that transforms each one of the input features (predictors) to min/max scale (i.e. [0,1] scale). The formula is given as follows:

$$X = \frac{x - x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \quad (10)$$

494 where X is the normalized data, x is the raw data, x_{min} is the minimum value of
495 each feature vector, and x_{max} is the maximum value of each feature vector.

496 It should be mentioned that the above two steps, namely the data acquisition and
497 feature extraction as well as the preprocessing could be performed iteratively taking into
498 consideration historical flood events in a specific region. As a result, a Flood Inventory
499 would be created that will be exploited to fit Machine Learning models capable to assess
500 the flood hazard.

501 4.1.4. Training, Testing and Validation

502 In this phase, various Machine Learning methodologies are applied to aim to assess
503 the flood hazard relied on the information from the Flood Inventory. The goal is to
504 select the best machine learning model in terms of precision in the estimation of flood
505 hazards. To achieve this, the dataset is divided randomly into two subsets. One portion
506 of 70% of the data is commonly utilised for training and the rest 30% for testing so
507 as to evaluate the capability of each model for generalisation. In this work, we use
508 four different machine learning approaches, namely Naïve Bayes (NB), Random Forest
509 (RF), Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Neural Networks (NN). The accuracy of each
510 model is estimated in terms of the statistical validation measures, such as Accuracy,
511 Precision, Recall and F-measure as well as the corresponding Confusion Matrix. The
512 outcome (target) of the Machine Learning model is the Flood Hazard Index (H) which is
513 estimated for every pixel on the area of interest and takes values between 0 and 1. Flood
514 Hazard Index represents the probability of flood occurrence in an area of interest and
515 classified into three (3) categories, namely Moderate, Medium and High.

516 4.1.5. Flood Hazard assessment and mapping

517 The above process results in the classification of each pixel in terms of the level of
518 severity of a potential flooding event that expressed by the Flood Hazard Index. To color
519 the necessary labels of the Flood Hazard categories, we followed coloring suggestions
520 by end-users (AAWA). The outcome of this process is a flood hazard map.

521 4.2. Dynamic Flood Risk Assessment Algorithm

522 To estimate the Hydraulic Flood Risk, it is necessary to calculate three basic pa-
523 rameters, namely the Flood Hazard, the Vulnerability and the Exposure, as mentioned
524 above. The first parameter relates with the Flood Hazard Index which is estimated
525 by adopting the process that proposed in Section 4.1 by fusing information from the
526 analysis of Satellite images and GIS-related data.

527 The other two parameters are the Vulnerability and Exposure of socioeconomic
528 elements in the impacted area. The flood risk assessment algorithm presented in this
529 work has been developed in collaboration by AAWA, as an adaptation of the procedure
530 presented in AAWA's Flood Risk Management Plan (FRMP) of the Eastern Alps River
531 Basin District. FRMP has been redacted by AAWA in compliance with the Directive
532 2007/60/EU, which also prescribes a periodic update of the contents of the plan every
533 six year. The first iteration of the plan was finalized in 2015 and approved in 2016 [44],
534 while the second iteration (referring to the period 2022-2028) is being finalized [55]. From
535 first to second cycle, some of the criteria have been updated. The methodology presented
536 in this work is coherent with the newest criteria.

537 According to the Flood Risk Management Plan (FRMP), for the estimation of the
538 Vulnerability and Exposure crucial and necessary is the knowledge of the usage and
539 land cover of the area of interest. Therefore, in this work we employ geospatial data

540 files, such as Corine Land Cover [56]. Then, a specific land use type from FRMP
 541 is corresponded with Corine Land Cover Codex (CLC) and the Manning roughness
 542 coefficient is estimated [44].

543 4.2.1. Vulnerability estimation

544 To mitigate the consequences of flood disasters, suitable Disaster Risk Reduction
 545 (DRR) measures need to be carried out. In addition to flood hazard awareness and
 546 knowledge, also information on Elements at Risk (EaR), i.e., people, infrastructure and
 547 assets, that may suffer damage when exposed to a flood hazard, needs to be consid-
 548 ered [57]. EaR's vulnerability assessment toward the specific flood hazard at different
 549 event magnitudes, and the resulting risk allows the effectively monitored and early
 550 warnings to be given in case in an impending hazardous situation.

551 In this work, the Flood Risk Assessment algorithm defines three different param-
 552 eters of vulnerability: *vulnerability of people (Vp)*, *vulnerability of economic activities (Ve)* and
 553 *vulnerability of environments and cultural-archaeological assets and protected areas (Va)*, all
 554 these parameters are estimate for every pixel and their values are between 0 and 1. These
 555 values depend both on the intrinsic characteristics of the different exposed assets, as
 556 well as the hydraulic condition (water level and water depth) that are established during
 557 the flood and they can affect the capacity of response. In other words, Vulnerability is
 558 dependent on the specific nature of the element, which can be related to land use, and
 559 simultaneously by the flood hazard. In the FRMP, a detailed description behind the
 560 definition of these rules is provided [44].

- 561 • **Vulnerability of people (Vp):** The physical vulnerability associated with people
 562 considers the values of flow velocity (Water Velocity - v) and Water Depth (h) that
 563 produce "instability" with respect to remaining in an upright position [58]. FRMP
 564 proposes a semi-quantitative equation that links a flood hazard index, referred
 565 to as the *Flood Hazard Rating (FHR)*, to h , v and a factor related to the amount of
 566 transported debris, i.e. the Debris Factor (DF). According to this algorithm, the land
 567 use type classes are grouped in order to calculate the Debris Factor (DF) concerning
 568 the possibility of floating materials which can harm the population.
 After the calculation of DF, the estimation of the Flood Hazard Rating (FHR) is
 carried out, by utilizing the Water Depth and Water Velocity according to the
 following formula:

$$FHR = h * (v + 0.5) + DF \quad (11)$$

569 where h is the Water Depth, v is the Water Velocity and DF is the Debris Factor. Vp
 570 is estimated according FHR (Table 2)

Table 2. Estimation of Vulnerability of people according to FHR.

FHR	Vp ($0 \leq Vp \leq 1$)
$FHR < 0.75$	0.25
$0.75 \leq FHR < 1.25$	0.75
$FHR \geq 1.25$	1

- 571 • **Vulnerability of economic activities (Ve):** The vulnerability associated with eco-
 572 nomic activities considers buildings, network infrastructure and agricultural areas
 573 [58]. It is a pixel-by-pixel function of the Water Depth (height) and Water Velocity
 574 (flow velocity). The vulnerability function depends on the specific nature of the
 575 assets and thus different functions are applied to land use types.
- 576 • **Vulnerability of environments and cultural-archaeological assets and protected
 577 areas (Va):** Environmental flood susceptibility is described using contamination/
 578 pollution and erosion as indicators. Contamination is caused by industry, animal/
 579 human waste and stagnant flooded waters. Erosion can produce disturbance

580 to the land surface and to vegetation but can also damage infrastructure [58].From
 581 AAWA's FRMP [44,55], the value of V_a in certain land use is 1, while assuming a
 582 residual V_a value for all other.

583 4.2.2. Exposure estimation

584 Exposure depends on the spatial collocation of the assets, which is strictly related
 585 to the land use, and on the evaluation of the potential negative consequence for each
 586 category of the exposed element. Flood risk algorithm sets three different exposure
 587 parameters: *exposure of people* (E_p), *exposure of economic activity* (E_e), *exposure of environment*
 588 *and cultural elements* (E_a). All these parameters are estimate for every pixel and their
 589 values are between 0 and 1. For more detailed information about the literature behind
 590 the definition of these rules, we remand to the FRMP [44,55].

- 591 • **Exposure of people (Ep):** First step to calculate the E_p , is to estimate the population
 592 of the area of interest per pixel which is divided into census areas by the Italian
 593 national Institute of Statistics (ISTAT). The dataset of population is given to us
 594 via shapefiles which is a form of geospatial vectors, so we can calculate per pixel
 595 according to geolocation data. The calculation of E_p can be produced by:

$$E_p = F_d * F_t \quad (12)$$

596 where F_d is a factor characterizing the density of the population in relation to the
 597 number of people present. For the population estimations in specific areas, census
 598 data have been employed. F_t is the proportion of time spent in different locations
 599 (e.g. houses and schools), using the land use classes.

- 600 • **Exposure of economic activity (Ee):** The E_e calculation depends solely on land use
 601 of the area of interest.
- 602 • **Exposure of environment and cultural elements (Ea):** As with E_e , exposure of
 603 environment and cultural elements – E_a , is estimates solely of land use.

604 4.2.3. Hydraulic Flood Risk Assessment

605 Considering we have all the estimations (Hazard, Vulnerability, Exposure) per pixel,
 606 we can calculate the Hydraulic Flood Risk [44,55,58] using the following formula:

$$R = \frac{p_p H * E_p * V_p + p_e H * E_e * V_e + p_a H * E_a * V_a}{p_p + p_e + p_a} \quad (13)$$

607 where H is the Flood Hazard, E is the Exposure, V is the Vulnerability and p_p p_e p_a
 608 are the weight parameters derived from FRMP [44,55]:

- 609 • $p_p = 10$, if there are inhabitants
- 610 • $p_e = 1$, if there are economic activities
- 611 • $p_a = 1$, if there are environments and cultural-archaeological assets and protected
 612 areas

613 The Hydraulic Flood Risk categorization is performed using the Table 3 bellow
 614 [44,55]:

Table 3. Classification of Hydraulic Risk into four classes

Risk R	Level of risk	Color
$0 \leq R < 0.2$	Moderate	Very light lime green
$0.2 \leq R < 0.5$	Medium	Soft yellow
$0.5 \leq R < 0.9$	High	Soft orange
$0.9 \leq R \leq 1.0$	Very High	Very light red

615 In order to create the corresponding Flood Risk Map for the area of interest, the
 616 assessments of the Hydraulic Flood Risk correspond to specific colors in RGB scale.

617 5. Results and Discussion

618 In order to evaluate the performance of the Dynamic Flood Hazard Assessment
619 algorithm in terms of its accuracy, firstly the machine learning models need to be created.
620 This takes place in the Training/Testing phase (Sec. 4.1.4) of the proposed methodological
621 framework. Then, in the evaluation phase, the trained models are validated in terms
622 of their precision, namely to estimate the class of Flood Hazard Index over “unknown”
623 data.

624 For this purpose, a series of experiments were realised in order to find out the best
625 set of parameters during the training of machine learning models which will result in
626 the chosen of the best model. The dataset that we used in this phase, formed based on
627 satellite images and DEM data over specific dates where floods had occurred, due to
628 the appearance of extremely high sea tides and heavy rains that were observed in the
629 municipality of Trieste.

630 As mentioned above, the dataset divided into two sets, 70% of the entries used
631 for training purposes and the rest 30% for testing the accuracy of the models. Cross-
632 Validation k-fold in order to evaluate the machine learning models is used. In our case,
633 the parameter k is set equal to 10 choosing the best model with the help of the average
634 results. A set of parameters for each one of the machine learning model that they have
635 been employed and evaluated is presented in the Table 4.

Table 4. Set of parameters per machine learning model

Model	Set of Parameters
Random Forest	Criterion: {Gini, Entropy}, Maxfeatures: {Auto, Log2, Sqrt, None}, n_Estimator: {50, 100, 200, 500}
Naïve Bayes	α : {0.01, 0.1, 1}
SVM	Kernel Functions: { rbf, poly, sigmoid }
Neural Network	Activation Function: {ReLu, Sigmoid}, #Neurons: {1, 2, 4, 6, 8}, Epochs: {100, 300, 500}

636 Table 5 presents the experimental results over the evaluation metrics Precision,
637 Recall and F1-Score achieved during the training of the machine learning models. Based
638 on these metrics, the selection of the best model was done using the methodology of
639 best_estimator (sklearn library). Random Forest was selected as best model, using the
640 hyperparameters: *Criterion: Gini, Max features: Auto, n_Estimator: 50*) as it achieved the
641 best performance, its average precision is approximately 0.9999995. The evaluation of
642 the model with the most efficient hyperparameters in relation to 30% of the data as a test
643 set, is shown in Figure 4 below, which depicts the Confusion Matrix.

Table 5. Summary table of results of the best-trained machine learning models over the test set

Model	Categories	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Random Forest (Criterion: Gini, Max features: Auto, n_Estimator: 50)	High Hazard	0.99	0.99	0.99
	Medium Hazard	0.99	0.99	0.99
	Moderate Hazard	0.99	0.99	0.99
Naïve Bayes (α : 0.01)	High Hazard	0.93	0.91	0.92
	Medium Hazard	0.91	0.97	0.94
	Moderate Hazard	0.00	0.00	0.00
SVM (Kernel Function: poly)	High Hazard	0.96	0.98	0.97
	Medium Hazard	0.96	0.99	0.98
	Moderate Hazard	0.98	0.97	0.98
Neural Network (Act.Fun.: ReLu, #Neur.: 8, Epochs: 500)	High Hazard	0.99	0.99	0.99
	Medium Hazard	0.99	0.99	0.99
	Moderate Hazard	0.99	0.99	0.99

Figure 4. Confusion Matrix of the best Random Forest model

644 Furthermore, the relative importance of the features namely the significance of each
645 one of the attributes that participated in the training of a machine learning model was
646 examined and the results are illustrated in the following figure (Figure 5):

Figure 5. Features Relative Importance of the best Random Forest model

647 The estimation of the features' relative importance was carried out by employing
 648 the best ML model, namely the Random Forest method. The features *Water Velocity* and
 649 *Water Depth* exhibit a significant role in the training and the inference of the ML model
 650 as in total their relative scores approximate 66% (Table 6). The *Slope* and *Roughness* of the
 651 terrain indicate quite high importance so that the trained model can classify in terms
 652 of the severity levels the input patterns. The other geomorphological factors, such as
 653 *Elevation (DEM)*, *TRI*, *TPI* and *Aspect* as well as the *Water Mask* do not evince to be so
 654 importance in the training process. An explanation of this could be the fact that the study
 655 area is coastal, smoothness and without significant differences in elevation. Moreover,
 656 the lack of variability in the values that the *Water Mask* receives is another reason to
 657 justify the low relative importance of this feature. The *Water Mask* implies the existence
 658 of water or not in a pixel, consequently, the inundated pixels are significantly less than
 659 the dry ones, in the dataset.

Table 6. Relative Importance scores of the features

Feature	Relative Importance score
Water Velocity	43.75939
Water Depth	22.99143
Slope	13.60606
Roughness	11.90979
DEM	3.87064
TRI	2.73504
TPI	0.23988
Water Mask	0.84437
Aspect	0.04339

660 5.1. Evaluation of Dynamic Flood Hazard/Risk algorithm

661 The goal of these experiments is to evaluate the performance of Dynamic Flood
 662 Hazard algorithm concerning its capability to produce accurate flood hazard maps,
 663 when the flood hazard assessment carries out using the best trained RF model.

664 For this purpose, the dataset that we employed was generated by satellite images
 665 and GIS data in the areas of Trieste, Muggia and Monfalcone following similar process
 666 as that we have already presented above. The satellite images refer to historical flood
 667 events, due to the high sea tides, "unknown" to the trained RF model.

668 Similarly, to evaluate the performance of the Dynamic Flood Risk Algorithm, we
 669 extend the former analysis over the evaluation datasets that have created by utilised the
 670 satellite imageries in the areas of interest for various dates. The goal is to estimate the
 671 Hydraulic Flood Risk (R) for each entry in the dataset, assign its value to a corresponding
 672 risk level and create the corresponding Flood Risk Map.

673 **Trieste 2019/09/23**

675 The confusion matrix (Figure 6) implies the efficacy of the proposed approach as
 676 the algorithm manage to inference correctly the entries of the validation dataset into the
 677 corresponding flood hazard labels (Predicted labels). In Figure 7 and Figure 8 the flood
 678 hazard and risk map in the Trieste area at 2019/09/23 are exhibited respectively.
 679

Figure 6. Confusion Matrix for best trained Random Forest model over Trieste, 2019/09/23 dataset in Validation Phase.

Figure 7. Flood Hazard map for Trieste at 2019/09/23.

Figure 8. Flood Risk map for Trieste at 2019/09/23.

680 **Muggia 2018/10/29**

681

682 Similarly, the results of the application of the proposed approach is also examined in
 683 the Muggia area at 2018/10/29. The confusion matrix (Figure 9) indicates the efficiency
 684 of the proposed approach. The flood hazard and risk map in the specific area and date
 685 are illustrated in the following figures (Figure 10 and Figure 11) respectively.

Figure 9. Confusion Matrix for best trained Random Forest model over Muggia, 2018/10/29 dataset in Validation Phase.

Figure 10. Flood Hazard map for Muggia at 2018/10/29.

Figure 11. Flood Risk map for Muggia at 2018/10/29.

686 **Monfalcone 2019/09/24**

687

688 The proposed approach managed to classify correctly the pixels, that shape the
 689 evaluation set in the Monfalcone area on 2019/09/24. The results are depicted in the
 690 corresponding confusion matrix (Figure 12). The Figure 13 and Figure 14 illustrate
 691 the flood hazard and risk map in the Monfalcone area at 2019/09/24 are exhibited
 692 respectively.

Figure 12. Confusion Matrix for best trained Random Forest model over Monfalcone, 2019/09/24 dataset in Validation Phase.

Figure 13. Flood Hazard map for Monfalcone at 2019/09/24.

Figure 14. Flood Risk map for Monfalcone at 2019/09/24.

693 5.2. Discussion

694 In this work, the proposed framework aims to provide to the Authorities a method-
 695 ology for evaluating and mapping the level of the risk of a specific flood event using free
 696 data from widely available sources, namely the satellite (Sentinal-1) data and GIS-related
 697 data. Initially, four well-known machine learning approaches, namely Naïve Bayes (NB),
 698 Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Neural Networks (NN), have
 699 been employed to fuse the available information and estimate in near real-time the flood
 700 hazard levels. From the experimental evaluation process, Random Forest has exhibited
 701 slightly better performance in terms of the F1-score compared with the others. Therefore,
 702 we used this approach, as a predictor, in order to create flood hazard maps in the region
 703 of the three Municipalities (Trieste, Muggia and Monfalcone) during the evaluation
 704 process. The high-precision scores achieved during the training and evaluation process

705 by machine learning algorithms are mainly due to the pixel-based approach that we
706 followed, instead to analyse a sampling of pixels. Hence, the trained machine learning
707 algorithms are able to classify correctly areas in terms of their flood hazard levels. Going
708 a step further, a rule-based approach has been applied, based on the AAWA's FRMP,
709 which combines the flood hazard assessments with flood exposure and vulnerability
710 estimations from the region of interest. The final goal was to produce a near real-time
711 flood risk map.

712 Concerning the flood conditioning factors, it should be mentioned that the impor-
713 tance of the flood conditioning factors depends on the geomorphological characteristics
714 in the area of interest as well as the historical flood events that were examined [22,59]. In
715 this work, the Water Velocity, Water Depth, Slope and Roughness have a dominant role
716 (approx. 91.5%) to the training and evaluation of the machine learning approaches that
717 were applied. This is a rational conclusion due to the fact that these factors affect the
718 propagation of flood and are the most important hydrodynamic parameters. Slope and
719 roughness affect flow velocity and the water depth. As more an area is smooth and steep
720 the more is higher the velocity of the flood. On the other hand, high roughness slows
721 the water flow but increases the water level. Moreover, as described in the Section 3.1,
722 the study areas are characterized by low slope and elevation of the ground above sea
723 level (coastal areas), which are factors that favor floods due to high tides.

724 Furthermore, water depth and water velocity, as described in the Section 4 are the
725 basis for both hazard and vulnerability estimations. These two factors participate in the
726 annotation process in order to classify each pixel in one of the severity level categories
727 (Section 4.1.3). The lack of annotated datasets to train machine learning models that
728 will enable the assessment of the flood hazard levels is considered a crucial issue for
729 the development of a robust system [5,16]. In this work, to overcome this limitation, an
730 automated rule-based approach has been adopted which inspired by the AAWA's FRMP.

731 In general, the proposed framework enables Authorities to evaluate the flood risk
732 in near real-time by utilising low cost or free of charge satellite data and thus it can
733 be used to overcome the gap of information in the areas with an irregular diffusion of
734 hydro-meteorological sensors. Additionally, even in the presence of legacy Decision
735 Support Systems like monitoring water distribution networks or forecasting systems,
736 the proposed framework can provide useful providing complementary information.

737 For example, hydrometers record a punctual measure of water level inside a fluvial
738 section. Thus, in the case of river overtopping, they cannot offer any useful information
739 about the extension of the flood external to the river, as well as about its impact on
740 the exposed assets. Similar consideration applies to flood forecasting system based on
741 1D hydraulic models. Even in the case of the availability of 2D hydraulics models, the
742 information provided is limited to a hazard estimation, while the concept of risk is really
743 crucial for effective response to an emergency situation and mitigating the consequences.
744 Flood Risk in fact links together not only the intensity of the event itself (hazard) but also
745 the potential impacts of the communities, economic assets, environment and cultural
746 heritage.

747 For this reason, the Flood Directive (2007/60/EC) highlights the importance of the
748 redaction of flood risk maps as part of flood management plans. However, flood risk
749 maps should be referred to a set of pre-defined hydraulic and hydrological scenarios
750 (floods of certain return times), which may be different from the ones that occur during
751 a real extreme event. From this perspective, this work aims to provide to the Authorities,
752 as an integration to the 'static' flood risk maps, a 'dynamic' tool for having a quick
753 and reliable estimation of the level of risk referred to a specific flood event when it
754 occurs. Moreover, the proposed methodology can be used to assess the risk caused by
755 different flooding mechanisms, including the ones that are currently not dealt by the
756 Flood Directive (e.g. urban flood).

757 Finally, the proposed approach can be used to help the calibration of 2D hydraulic
758 models, which is a challenging and time-consuming process. That means the operators

759 have to simulate a flood event based on the past events for whom hydrometer's record-
760 ings/measurements are available. Then, they should confirm whether the results of the
761 model are coherent with those measurements. However, measurements are punctual (a
762 hydrometer measures the water level in a specific place, called river section) whereas
763 the 2D model covers a broader area. Hence, the calibration of a 2D model that covers a
764 vast area by using only sparse punctual values is not an easy task. Moreover, although it
765 is very important to calibrate a 2D model in surrounding areas of the river, however, the
766 hydrometers are located inside the river and as a result, the water level measurements in
767 the flooding areas (areas outside the river due to overtopping) do not available.

768 6. Conclusions

769 In flood management studies, the creation of accurate flood hazard and risk maps is
770 essential for the preparedness and mitigation of an extreme flood incident. In the recent
771 decade, numerous researches have been published aiming to assess the flood hazard
772 and create more reliable hazard maps. State-of-the-art methodologies utilise advanced
773 remote sensing techniques including Satellite imagery analytical tools and GIS-related
774 data along with machine learning techniques aiming to estimate the flood susceptibility
775 and develop the corresponding maps. In this work, a flood hazard assessment algorithm
776 proposed which deals with the problem of flood monitoring and mapping. It develops a
777 machine learning model which is enabled to assess the severity levels of flood hazard.
778 The utilisation of satellite imagery along with the flood conditioning factors that are
779 generated by GIS, provide the opportunity to create an extensive flood inventory. The
780 proposed approach attempts to resolve the two main challenges which are:

- 781 1. the domain lack of annotated dataset for the training and evaluation of the machine
782 learning techniques able to detect and monitor the flood event by utilisation remote
783 sensing techniques.
- 784 2. the low temporal frequency of satellite imagery acquisition, which hinders the
785 real-time monitoring of an evolving flood.

786 Furthermore, in this paper an extension of the Dynamic Flood Hazard algorithm was
787 realised in order to estimate the hydraulic flood risk combining vulnerability and ex-
788 posure information from impacted areas. Both approaches are evaluated in terms of
789 their accuracy and their capability to create accurate flood hazard and flood risk maps.
790 The results are quite promising and encouraging. However, improvements should be
791 done in the direction of the integration social media information into the Flood Risk
792 algorithm.

793 Another aspect that we should deal with is the reduce the processing time and
794 computational effort. These are mainly affected by the resolution of the satellite imagery,
795 the DEM and the other derived flood conditioning factors. Due to the pixel-based
796 approach that was followed in the analysis, higher resolutions of the images generate
797 bigger scale datasets, which are demanding to resources. On the other hand, a poor
798 resolution of the images affects the quality of the flood hazard and risk assessments
799 and the generated maps. Hence, we should find out a trade-off between the quality of
800 images and framework robustness. A potential solution to increase the quality of the
801 DEM or its unavailability, is the adoption of low-cost UAV applications.

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805 Abbreviations

806 The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

AAWA	Alto Adriatico Water Authority
AHP	Analytical Hierarchy Process
AoI	Area of Interest
ANNs	Artificial Neural Networks
CART	Classification and Regression Trees
CRCL	Crisis Classification
CLC	Corine Landcover Codex
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
EaR	Elements at Risk
Ep	Exposure of people
Ee	Exposure of economic activity
Ea	Exposure of environment and cultural elements
FFPI	Flash-Flood Potential Index
FHR	Flood Hazard Rating
FR	Frequency Ratio
807 FRMP	Flood Risk Management Plan
GIS	Geographical Information System
LIDAR	Laser Imaging, Detection And Ranging
LR	Logistic Regression
LULC	Land Use Land Cover
MDA	Multivariate Discriminant Analysis
NNs	Neural Networks
RF	Random Forest
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SNAP	Sentinel Application Platform
SVMs	Support Vector Machines
TRI	Terrain Ruggedness Index
TWI	Topographic Wetness Index
UAVs	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
Vp	Vulnerability of people
Ve	Vulnerability of economic activities
Va	Vulnerability of environments and cultural-archaeological assets and protected areas

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